

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF MERCAPTANS WITH HALOGEN CYANIDES AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

Mercaptan	Determination with ICN					Determination with BrCN				
	Time hr.	Temp. °C	Amount of mercaptan (mg)			Time hr.	Temp. °C	Amount of mercaptan (mg)		
			Taken	Found	% Error			Taken	Found	% Error
Propyl mercaptan	3.0	80-90	37.00	37.06	+0.16	3.0	80-90	37.50	37.56	+0.16
			18.50	18.53	+0.16			18.50	18.48	-0.10
			9.25	9.24	-0.11			10.50	10.49	-0.10
2-Mercaptoethanol	1.5	60-70	34.24	34.22	-0.06	1.5	60-70	34.16	34.18	+0.06
			17.60	17.58	-0.11			17.40	17.38	-0.12
			8.80	8.81	+0.11			10.40	10.38	-0.19
Cysteamine hydrochloride	1.5	70-80	35.40	35.32	-0.22	1.5	60-70	31.36	31.33	-0.09
			25.04	25.02	-0.08			20.66	20.65	-0.05
			15.02	15.05	+0.19			10.33	10.35	+0.20
Thio- <i>p</i> -cresol	1.0	50-60	24.03	24.07	+0.16	1.5	60-70	30.24	30.20	-0.11
			18.10	18.09	-0.06			25.05	25.08	+0.12
			12.07	12.09	-0.08			20.30	20.33	+0.15
Thioacetic acid	3.0	25-30	36.84	36.88	+0.10	1.0	25-30	36.50	36.50	+0.00
			30.85	30.83	-0.06			24.35	24.37	+0.08
			24.56	24.59	+0.12			18.45	18.43	-0.10
Thioglycolic acid	2.0	80-90	34.55	34.52	-0.09	2.0	80-90	32.50	32.47	-0.09
			24.34	24.38	+0.16			26.84	26.91	+0.26
			20.65	20.62	-0.10			18.76	18.78	+0.10
Ethylmercaptoacetate	1.5	60-70	48.65	48.70	+0.10	1.5	60-70	41.75	41.71	-0.08
			36.95	37.00	+0.14			35.32	35.35	+0.09
			24.74	24.71	-0.12			24.38	24.40	+0.08

reactions may be attributed to the formation of the corresponding sulphenyl halide.

The formation of sulphenyl iodide and bromide on reacting the mercaptans with iodine and bromine respectively has already been reported⁷.

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Potentiometric (*pH*-metric) study of In(III) complexes with α -hydroxy acids

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THE metal chelates of In(III) with mandelic acid have been studied potentiometrically and compared with that of glycollic and lactic acids. The formation constants of mandelic acid chelates ML , ML_2 , and ML_3 formed in stepwise and the overall formation constant, β_3 , calculated by Calvin-Bjerrum method at $\mu = 0.1M$ (NaClO_4) and 30° are : $\text{Log } K_1 = 3.30$, $\text{Log } K_2 = 3.23$, $\text{Log } K_3 = 2.29$ and $\text{Log } \beta_3 = 8.82$. The stability order $\text{Lac} > \text{Gly} > \text{Man}$. is in agreement with the order of basic strength of the ligands.

TABLE I—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF α -HYDROXY ACIDS COMPLEXES WITH In(III)

	$\mu = 0.10 M (NaClO_4)$								
	In(III)-Mandelate			In(III)-Glycollate			In(III)-Lactate		
	30°	40°	50°	30°	40°	50°	30°	40°	50°
Log K_1	3.30	3.28	3.23	3.42	3.32	3.28	3.65	3.61	3.55
Log K_2	3.23	3.19	3.16	2.98	2.95	2.85	3.32	3.30	3.24
Log K_3	2.29	2.26	2.23	2.66	2.62	2.55	2.95	2.90	2.81
Log β_3	8.82	8.73	8.61	9.06	8.89	8.68	9.92	9.81	9.60

In earlier communications^{1,2} from our laboratory stability constants and thermodynamic parameters of glycolates and lactates of In(III) were discussed. In the present communication are reported the step-wise formation constants of In(III) complexes with mandelic acid and compared with that reported earlier for glycolates and lactates of the metal by Chakrawarti *et al.*^{1,2}

All the chemicals used were of either B.D.H. (Analar) or equivalent quality. Standard solutions of the ligand and the metal salt were prepared in doubly distilled water, pH of the solutions were measured using 'Systronics', type 322, pH meter.

Formation constants were calculated by Calvin-Bjerrum's method³ at three temperatures 30°, 40° and 50° in 0.1M ($NaClO_4$) ionic strength. The values of log K_1 , log K_2 and log K_3 were directly read from the formation curve and are recorded in Table I. The corresponding values for glycolic and lactic acids complexes, reported earlier by Chakrawarti *et al.*^{1,2} are also recorded in Table I for comparison.

The pH titrations reveal that in In(III)-mandelic acid system, a precipitate appears at pH ~ 4.55 (cf. ~ 4.60 pH in cases of In(III)-glycolic acid and In(III)-lactic acid systems).

From the formation curves [$\bar{n}$ vs $p[L^-]$] of the metal chelates with mandelic acid, it is observed that in all the cases $\bar{n} \sim 3$ (before precipitation points) thus confirming the formation of three chelates, ML , ML_2 and ML_3 as indicated by pH-metric ratio titrations using Nair and Pande's monovariation method⁴.

The stability order of In(III) complexes with the α -hydroxy acids found is lactates > glycolates > mandelates, which is also the order of the basic strength of the ligands.

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Chemical Studies on the Polysaccharides of the seeds of *Phaseolus mungo*

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THE polysaccharide of the seeds of *Phaseolus mungo* (Eng. Black gram) has been the subject of study since it is one of the important pulses cultivated throughout India. Different important products like vitamins¹, amino acids², total soluble sugars³ and mucopolysaccharides⁴ have been isolated from the various parts of the plant.

The seeds were freed from skins, macerated, defatted, deproteinised⁵ and different fractions of polysaccharides were isolated according to the scheme described earlier⁶. The powdered material (30 g) was extracted successively with (1) cold water, (2) boiling water, (3) 0.1N sodium hydroxide solution, and (4) 1.0N sodium hydroxide solution. In the case of water extraction two fractions could be isolated from each of the extracts, the first fraction coming out on addition of minimum quantity of ethanol while the second was precipitated by the addition of excess quantity of ethanol to the supernatant liquid, left after separation of the first fraction. In the case of alkali extraction first fraction was obtained by acidification of the extract to pH 5.0 with 50% aqueous acetic acid solution and the second fraction was precipitated by addition of sufficient quantity of ethanol. Eight fractions were isolated and these were designated as M_1 , M_2 , M_3 , M_4 , M_5 , M_6 , M_7 , and M_8 respectively. Yield: M_1 —0.42 g; M_2 —0.11 g; M_3 —4.10 g; M_4 —0.42 g; M_5 —1.10 g; M_6 —0.81 g; M_7 —0.36 g; M_8 —1.20 g.

The monosaccharide components present in the isolated polysaccharides were identified⁷ by paper chromatography and TLC (solvent systems—ethyl acetate : pyridine : water, 8 : 2 : 1; *n*-butanol : ethanol : water, 5 : 1 : 4; ethyl acetate : pyridine : acetic acid : water, 5 : 5 : 1 : 3; spraying reagents—alkaline solution of silver nitrate and aqueous solution of aniline oxalate (saturated). The ratios of sugar components were estimated by periodate oxidation method⁸ and also colorimetrically. Moisture percentage, ash percentage and optical rotations (0.5% in 0.5N NaOH) were measured. All evaporations